

WEB3 FOR UKRAINE:

TALK TO FOUNDERS

Ministry
of Digital Transformation
of Ukraine

OVERVIEW

Web3 as a new sector of the digital economy has great economic and social potential and can play an important role in the recovery and development of Ukraine.

The Web3 Institute team, with the support of the Ministry of Digital Transformation in Ukraine, conducted a series of interviews with 50 Ukrainian web3 founders from 19 sectors of the web3 economy. The topic of the interviews was: challenges and opportunities for the development of the respondents' businesses and the web3 space in Ukraine generally. The results of this series of interviews are summarized in this report "Web3 for Ukraine: Talk to Founders".

Summary of results by theme:

War. The full-scale Russian invasion has resulted in Ukrainian web3 startups facing currency restrictions, travel restrictions, and poses risks for foreign investors, partners, and customers.

Education. There are three aspects to the education deficit in web3: the general education of web3 users, higher education for professionals working in the space, and upskilling, particularly for government officials.

Startup Ecosystem. In Ukraine, the ecosystem for web3 startups (hackathons, incubators, accelerators) is not developed, there is no community of founders or support programs for web3 startups.

Investment. Venture investing in web3 is not developed in Ukraine. It is increasingly difficult for web3 startups to attract venture capital. Startups try to compensate by applying for grants.

Buying web3 project tokens is an investment opportunity for Ukrainian retail investors facing limited access to the global stock market.

Tokenization. The tokenization of assets could: support activity on the Ukrainian stock market, contribute to the development of the real estate market (in particular the land market), create new markets and business models, and strengthen financial inclusion by simplifying access to retail investment opportunities. The development of tokenization in Ukraine is blocked by a lack of legislation.

Banking Services. Web3 startups do not have access to full-fledged banking services. Blocked money transfers related to the purchase and sale of crypto-assets prevent the launch of related web3 products and create inefficient and risky exchange schemes.

Regulatory uncertainty. Regulatory uncertainty makes it difficult for web3 startups to collaborate with government agencies. The lack of regulation forces web3 startups to incorporate in foreign jurisdictions. The uncertainty of taxation and the risk of retroactive application of laws are of particular concern to businesses and consumers. Similarly, the rights of consumers in the field of web3 and the mechanisms of their protection are not defined.

Private Sector Experience to Date. Web3 businesses have had unsatisfactory experiences interacting with regulatory bodies. They report a lack of interest in their needs and a lack of expertise from authorities. The risk that the “rules of the game” can be changed at any time without taking into account the interests of the business is assessed as significant.

MiCA. Ukraine is not ready for MiCA. Including the Ukrainian virtual asset market, the public authorities, and experts. Furthermore, Ukraine does not need a copy of MiCA. Rather, regulatory arbitrage in contrast with MiCA. In this regard, one of Ukraine’s competitive advantages may be the legalization of DAOs.

Regulatory Sandbox. Young web3 startups need a regulatory sandbox. This will lower the entry threshold for web3 founders and increase the pace of creation of web3 startups in Ukraine.

Virtual assets as a medium of exchange. The ban on the use of virtual assets as a means of exchange for goods and services almost completely blocks the functioning and development of the web3 economy.

Licensing and Standardization. Licensing and standardization are a necessary stage in the development of web3 technologies and the web3 economy. They strengthen the protection of the interests of investors and consumers. Professional associations can take on the role of developing standards for web products, professionals, and education.

Positioning of Ukraine in the web3 space. Ukraine must determine its positioning in the web3 space and develop a consistent strategy based on this. The country now has a resource in the form of relatively inexpensive technical talent. which needs to be preserved and nurtured into successful web3 product companies. There are a number of tools for attracting web3 companies to the Ukrainian jurisdiction. However, without solving the basic problems with the image of Ukraine as a rule-of-law and business-friendly state, these tools may be ineffective.

Web3 for the State. Ukraine is ahead of many developed countries in the level of digitalization (online banking, public services), and web3 technologies can strengthen its leadership in this area. There are many web3 projects, promising from the point of view of economic and social effects, which can be launched by the state in the form of pilots.

Mass adoption. The mass adoption of web3 depends on communicating the benefits and risks of web3 technologies to users. However, web3 projects must also solve real problems for users, be convenient and easy to use, and be worth paying for, to achieve mass adoption. Mass adoption also requires that companies implement web3 technologies in their products and business processes, and therefore on their awareness of the benefits and risks associated with implementing web3 technologies.

This report does not pretend to be a comprehensive or exhaustive coverage of the challenges and opportunities facing web3 development in Ukraine. Its goal is to communicate to all relevant stakeholders the perspectives of Ukrainian Web3 founders (incredibly relevant for the future of the space in Ukraine) and to initiate public discussion.

INTRODUCTION

Web3

Web3 is a set of public, peer-to-peer (P2P) computer networks that enable decentralized exchange, processing, and storage of data, as well as decentralized applications (both financial and non-financial) to run on these networks.

Web3 opens up new opportunities for individuals, businesses, the state, and non-profit organizations. New digital assets, goods and services, new business models, cost reduction in existing businesses, increased reliability and transparency of processes in a wide variety of industries — from supply chains and circulation of digital assets to public registries and voting — encompass the potential of web3.

The war has caused significant damage to the Ukrainian "analog" economy. Under these conditions, the development of the Ukrainian digital economy is an opportunity to increase employment and GDP quickly, when compared to more traditional industries. The presence of adequate state policies aimed at stimulating the development of web3 in Ukraine will contribute to this process. For this to happen, Ukraine needs a national strategy for the development of the digital economy, which includes consideration for the development of the web3 space.

Web3 for Ukraine: The Founders Report

Believing in the role that web3 can play in the recovery and development of Ukraine, the Public Union "Virtual Assets 2030" together with the Ministry of Digital Transformation of Ukraine initiated the study "Web3 for Ukraine: Talk to Founders". This research was conducted as a part of the Web3 Institute project, which was created to promote the development of Ukrainian web3 space, by generating research, educational initiatives, as well as pilot projects that support the public and private sector.

The goal of the report is to determine the challenges and opportunities facing individual web3 businesses and web3 space in Ukraine overall, by conducting a series of interviews with Ukrainian founders who are building web3-focused products or services.

The report outlines the results of this study, which are offered for public discussion to stakeholders in the private sector, government, and non-governmental organizations as well as the expert community and web3 users and advocates. This report is for everyone who is concerned with the Ukrainian digital economy and web3, and is interested in the promise of the web3 space for Ukrainian economic recovery and development.

Report Methodology

Preparation for the series of interviews began by grouping businesses within the web3 space into functional areas. 20 functional areas were determined as follows:

1. **Networks** are public, decentralized computer networks for data exchange, processing, and storage (L1 and L2).
2. **Miners and validators** are the parties (individuals or businesses) that process transactions in public decentralized networks (PoW and PoS).
3. **Wallets** are applications for managing private keys and transactions (including custodial and non-custodial).
4. **Exchange services** allow for the exchange of crypto assets (including both centralized exchanges and exchange offices).
5. **Payment processors** provide services for accepting payments in cryptocurrency and transfers of national currencies for buying and selling cryptocurrencies (on-ramp and off-ramp).
6. **Devshops** provide software development services in the field of web3.
7. **Hardware** providers produce devices for interaction with web3 (for example, hardware wallets, mining devices).
8. **Cyber security** companies provide security services for web3 projects, in particular code audits of public decentralized networks and decentralized applications.
9. **Blockchain analytics** projects offer tools for analyzing the history of transactions on public networks (for both crime-fighting and commercial purposes).
10. **DeFi** includes decentralized financial applications that operate on public networks.
11. **Oracles** are entities that supply external data to decentralized applications.
12. **NFTs and gaming** are products related to the issuance and circulation of non-fungible tokens (from digital art to gaming assets).
13. **Cross-chain infrastructure** is a set of services that provide communication between networks (in particular, for the transfer of assets between networks and the operation of decentralized cross-chain applications).
14. **Trading and asset management** are services related to trading and trust management of crypto assets.
15. **Investors** are venture funds that invest in web3 startups.
16. **Recruiting** projects provide recruitment services in the field of web3.
17. **Legal Services** are companies specializing in legal services in the web3 industry.
18. **Hackathons, incubators, accelerators** are projects aimed at creating conditions for the development of the ecosystem of web3 startups.
19. **Media and conferences** include mass media and conferences dedicated to web3.
20. **Marketing, PR, consulting** are agencies that provide web3 projects with marketing and PR services, as well as consulting on fundraising, business development, management, etc.

The goal was to conduct interviews with Ukrainian web3 founders from all areas, as each area has its own demands and challenges. For the purposes of this study, "Ukrainian web3 founders" means the founders of projects from the specified sectors who were born and raised in Ukraine. As a result, we managed to conduct interviews with fifty founders from nineteen sectors. But, we were unable to find founders that represent the "Hardware" category.

Interviews took place in the form of video calls lasting up to 60 minutes. The interviews were not recorded, but it was explained to the founders that findings would be published as generalized and anonymized qualitative research. The respondents were informed as to the context for the study under the Web3 Institute's goals. The open-ended interview format benefitted the study in two ways: firstly, it increased the likelihood of relevant and meaningful responses, and secondly, it prevented any confirmation bias from the interviewer.

The two topics discussed were: blockers and drivers of the founder's business and the web3 economy of Ukraine in general. The development of web3 was interpreted as an increase in the number of web3 users, web3 startups and their employees, investments and investors in these startups, as well as foreign web3 companies operating on the Ukrainian market.

In order to gather authentic perspectives, rather than test the institute's hypotheses, the interviews did not have a fixed list of questions. The founders could express their opinions on the two proposed topics freely. So, the emphasis and range of topics discussed were not always the same. Therefore, the results of this series of interviews do not contain any quantitative analysis. To preserve the integrity of the founder's ideas and feedback, we limited our analysis to grouping the answers of the founders according to the most popular themes and summarizing them in a single text.

FOUNDER DIALOGUE OUTCOMES

War

The full-scale invasion of Russia has resulted in Ukrainian web3 startups facing currency restrictions, travel restrictions, and is causing risks for foreign investors, partners, and customers.

Currency restrictions have made it difficult for Ukrainian web3 companies to manage their cash resources, in particular, to fulfill their financial obligations to counterparties.

Restrictions on leaving the country have greatly affected the possibilities of business development: international conferences are the main platform for business development, networking, and exchange of experiences. Potential investors want personal meetings. If the founders do not regularly attend international conferences and are not known in the web3 community, it is much more difficult for them to attract investments and partners. Organizing international conferences in Ukraine is currently also problematic.

Business development and fundraising for startups based in Ukraine is complicated by the fact that the presence of a startup team in a country at war is a significant risk for investors, partners, and customers.

The outflow of qualified web3 specialists from Ukraine reduces the supply in the domestic labor market. Demand for those who remained in the country is decreasing: investors, due to the risks of war, demand that startups hire workers outside of Ukraine. Some Ukrainian outsourcing companies have also started hiring more foreigners and positioning themselves as foreign companies in order not to lose potential customers. Some founders believe that the risks related to war posed an acute problem for foreign investors, partners and customers at the beginning of the full-scale invasion, and now their concerns are easing.

There was an opinion that investors who have startups with Russian roots in their portfolio are less willing to invest in Ukrainian startups.

There are cases when the initiatives of Ukrainian web3 projects to collect cryptocurrency donations for Ukraine did not find proper support and recognition from the authorities.

Education

There are three aspects of web3 education challenges: general education of web3 users, higher education of web3 specialists, and upskilling, including training for government officials.

In addition to a lack of basic digital and financial literacy, users have a poor understanding of the opportunities, benefits, and risks of using web3 and investing in web3 projects. Many people still have prejudices about web3 ("pyramid, scam, black market").

On the Ukrainian labor market, web3 projects face a shortage of high-quality non-technical expertise: marketers, business developers, managers, UX designers, financiers, tokenomists, traders, lawyers, journalists, blockchain researchers, and cultural figures. There is a lack of specialists with a product mindset, an understanding of web3 features, and fluent English. Respondents repeatedly expressed the idea that "there are few high-quality web3 specialists on the labor market because such specialists have their own startups."

Now, web3 business is forced to solve these problems on their own — companies hire capable employees and independently retrain them to the required level. This also applies to web3 programmers, since universities do not train such specialists, and with the development of web3, the demand for them will only grow.

Higher education institutions do not actively cooperate with businesses in the development of educational programs for web3 specialists. The opinion exists that cooperation with universities may not be effective enough, so it is better for businesses to develop educational products on their own.

It is not enough to just write new master's programs with an emphasis on web3 — we need appropriately trained teachers, which are non-existent now. The practice of internships, internships of students, graduate students, and teachers in industry companies and organizations is poorly developed.

Government officials have an insufficient understanding of web3 and the potential of this industry for economic development, which leads to inadequate relations with web3 businesses, particularly during the development and implementation of regulatory norms. The lack of a basic understanding of web3 is one of the reasons for distancing official cultural institutions from web3 and the community of Ukrainian artists experimenting with web3 technologies.

Startup Ecosystem

In Ukraine, there is no developed ecosystem for web3 startups (hackathons, incubators, accelerators), there is no school of founders and support programs for web3 startups.

There is no full-fledged ecosystem for web3 startups in Ukraine. From the "hackathon - incubator - pre-acceleration - accelerator" funnel, there are only sporadic hackathons that are not coordinated among themselves. Incubators and accelerators require full-time teams with relevant expertise — unlike hackathons, they cannot function solely on a volunteer basis.

There is no community of founders. There is no mechanism for transferring experience from more experienced founders to novice founders. Many young web3 founders have a poor connection between their project and real problems, lack business thinking and an understanding of the basic principles of launching and developing a startup. They often lack the ability to sell their product. Additionally, there is widespread focus on short-term projects, rather than the long-term building of unicorn companies. Founders are often unable to engage in professional communication with investors and ensure the protection of the investor interest, especially retail investors.

Respondents from outsourcing companies note that many clients who contact them regarding the development of web3 products lack subject matter expertise and business acumen.

Young founders are forced to gain experience on their own through trial and error, spending time and money. There are no educational, financial, regulatory, information, and promotional support programs for Ukrainian web3 startups. One Ukrainian web3 startup was not given a government grant for an idea that was later implemented in a reduced form by a foreign startup, which became a unicorn.

Investments

It has become more difficult for Web3 startups to attract venture capital. Startups are trying to at least partially compensate for the investment deficit with grants. Venture investing in web3 is not sufficiently developed in Ukraine. Buying web3 project tokens is an investment opportunity for Ukrainians in conditions of limited access to the global stock market.

The web3 space is very young and consists mostly of early-stage startups that are not yet sustainable. The main source of funding for the industry is investments from venture capital funds.

Now, it is much more difficult for web3 startups to attract investments. The market has become more mature, and venture capital funds have gained more experience and expertise. In addition, the market has not yet recovered from the large-scale crisis of 2022. Regulatory risks have increased, new narratives (such as artificial intelligence) have emerged, and it is more difficult for funds themselves to raise money with the increased cost of capital. Investors study web3 projects more carefully, put forward stricter requirements, and invest less willingly. Startups that have raised investments at high valuations in a bull market are now finding it more difficult to raise the next round of investment.

The lack of emphasis on the long-term creation of unicorn companies, mentioned above in the context of the development of a startup ecosystem, is often encouraged by venture capital funds themselves. Often, funds are interested in quickly capturing the return on investment through the sale of the startup's tokens — the prospect of a

rapid increase in the price of the token, rather than the long-term success of the product. The same can be said about retail investors in web3 startups. For startups, this strategy of investors can have negative consequences, so now some founders refuse to launch and sell a token in favor of selling a share in the company.

An alternative source of funding is grants from the foundations of L1 and L2 networks, but their grant policy does not always correspond to the interests of startups. However, for small teams without a legal entity, such cryptocurrency grants are an opportunity to survive the current downturn in the tech sector, in general, and web3 in particular.

Venture investing in web3 is not developed in Ukraine. The reasons are: the youth of the Ukrainian economy, the lack of relevant legislation, the insufficient amount and high price of financial resources on the Ukrainian market, the difficulty of attracting foreign capital to Ukrainian funds, the insufficient level of development of fund expertise in the field of web3 and the culture of venture investing in general, lack of "smart money".

The opinion exists that Ukrainian funds invest little in Ukrainian web3 startups in the early stages due to distrust of domestic founders. To attract investments from a Ukrainian fund, you need to either know the fund personally or first attract investments from a well-known foreign fund.

Large Ukrainian investors are usually more conservative: they are more willing to invest in foreign real estate than in web3 projects. The experience of the dotcom boom shows that Ukraine needs a new class of investors — successful founders from the world of the digital economy who will invest their capital via venture funds.

The web3 investment market is dominated by gray schemes (ICO, IDO, etc.). Despite the lack of protection of investors' rights in such schemes, for Ukrainian retail investors it is practically the only alternative to bank deposits and government bonds. At the same time, startups are not always ready to deal with Ukrainian investors who cannot pass AML compliance — for the founders, these are additional risks.

The main investments in web3 come from American funds, and it is more difficult for Ukrainian teams to attract investments from them than local ones. However, a really strong team with a strong idea has no problems with investments — funds compete for the opportunity to invest in such a startup. It was also thought that, despite the current difficulties in the market, it is generally easier for a web3 startup to attract investment than a web2 startup, since there is still less competition in the web3 industry and it is easier for startups to attract attention.

Tokenization

The tokenization of assets could support the Ukrainian stock market, promote the development of the real estate market (in particular the land market), the emergence

of new markets and business models, increase financial inclusion by simplifying access to investment, and increase the income of the population. The development of tokenization in Ukraine is blocked by the lack of the necessary legislation.

The national stock market is the basis for the development of local companies. Tokenization of assets, in particular real estate and shares in small and medium-sized businesses, can breathe life into the Ukrainian stock market and become a point of growth. This will make it easier for foreign investors and Ukrainian retail investors to access new investment sites in Ukraine and will provide Ukrainian enterprises with a new source of financing. In addition, web3 technologies allow issuing securities with greater functionality than conventional securities.

The initial offering and trading of tokenized Ukrainian assets can take place on Ukrainian licensed exchanges. These exchanges can undertake not only the verification of projects before listing but also subsequent regular audits. Ukrainians who became early investors in Ukrainian assets will take on more risk, but this risk will be compensated by higher income if successful.

Tokenization of real estate could enable the population to collect funds for the purchase of an apartment not in the form of cash, which depreciates due to inflation, or a bank deposit, but in the form of shares in real estate assets that grow in price and provide income. Tokenization can simplify the access of domestic and foreign investors to the Ukrainian land market. The same applies to government bonds.

Tokenization of art, intellectual property, game assets, and assets from the metaverse could create new markets and business models. These could provide new opportunities for artists, owners of intellectual rights, including museums, game development companies, and developers of financial products.

The technical solutions and ready-made products for tokenization are there - what is needed is a law governing the initial offering of virtual assets. In particular, there is a need for legislative regulation of crowdfunding: simplified conditions for financing projects, in particular through tokenization, within reasonable limits of the total amount of the collection and contribution per participant.

The regulation of tokenized assets should be governed by the content of the tokenized asset and the property rights associated with this asset that are transferred via the token. When developing legal norms for new classes of assets, the experience of leading jurisdictions can be useful: for example, the experience of Singapore in regulating the circulation of gaming assets (Payment Services Act 2019).

Banking Services

Web3 startups do not have access to full-fledged banking services. Blocked money transfers related to the purchase and sale of cryptocurrencies prevent the launch of related web3 products and create inefficient and risky exchange schemes.

Banks are reluctant to deal with web3 companies due to a lack of regulation. It is difficult for a web3 business to open a bank account or acquire banking services (for example, obtaining a loan to open a mining farm or using mining equipment as collateral for a loan). The opinion exists that a bank account is relevant only for working with a small number of counterparties since most want to pay with stablecoins, but the question of legal offramp remains open.

Blocking bank transactions related to the purchase and sale of cryptocurrencies (onramp and offramp) does not allow web3 businesses to launch their products in Ukraine and leads to the emergence of "self-made acquiring services" that do not benefit the state, businesses, and users. Blocking offramps also reduced the effectiveness of using cryptocurrency donations to support Ukraine.

Banks do not work with virtual assets, so web3 businesses have to look for ways to exchange cryptocurrencies in the gray area, which creates additional risks, particularly in the field of interaction with law enforcement agencies. Retail consumers also cannot legally receive national currency in their bank account in exchange for cryptocurrency. This makes life difficult for employees of web3 companies who are paid in stablecoins.

Although cryptocurrencies have been positioned as an alternative to banks since the beginning, banks can lead the mass adoption of web3. Banks already have a large customer base, public trust, experience, and resources. The reason why banks have not yet used this opportunity to its full extent is the high level of conservatism of these financial institutions.

Regulatory Uncertainty

Regulatory uncertainty makes it difficult for web3 startups to collaborate with government agencies. The lack of regulation forces web3 startups to incorporate in foreign jurisdictions. The uncertainty of taxation and the risk of retroactive application of laws are of particular concern to businesses and consumers. The rights of consumers in the field of web3 and the mechanisms of their protection are not defined.

Projects are ready to cooperate with government institutions and even provide them with their products free of charge, but the employees of the institutions themselves refuse to do so due to the lack of clear official rules for working with web3 technologies. For example, the use of NFT by museums to monetize their intellectual rights or by Ukrposhta to issue digital stamps.

The lack of a clear regulatory framework is one of the reasons for the incorporation of web3 companies abroad, in particular offshore. There are no clear legal regulations to register any startup related to virtual assets in Ukraine.

Startups need to be clear about two issues: how to structure investment rounds and their product (primarily financial products, but there are others — for example, NFT-based products). Another reason for offshore registration is the orientation of projects to the American market.

Web3 companies specializing in trading and asset management are forced to work exclusively with their own resources - they cannot attract capital from users due to the lack of regulation. In Ukraine, investment funds do not have mechanisms to legally purchase cryptocurrencies for fiat. There are no clear rules for the official work of Ukrainian web3 companies with foreign counterparties.

Currently, web3 businesses and web3 users do not have an understanding of how they should pay taxes on cryptocurrency income, but there are concerns about the retroactive application of laws once they are passed. For example, if every purchase and sale of crypto assets such as bitcoin is subject to VAT (in the EU these transactions are not subject to VAT) or income tax, then retroactive application of this rule to traders and asset managers can simply ruin them.

It is also worth mentioning the lack of certainty regarding the rights of consumers of virtual assets and web3 products, as well as the mechanisms for protecting these rights.

Public Private Interactions

Web3 businesses have had an unsatisfactory experience when interacting with regulatory bodies: founders feel that the authorities lack interest in their needs and expertise. Founders believe the risk that the "rules of the game" can be changed at any time without taking into account the interests of business are significant.

Web3 businesses anticipated the regulatory regime approved by the Law of Ukraine "On Virtual Assets", but later it was announced requirements would be much stricter than MiCA. Taxation was expected to stimulate the launch of the virtual asset market, but no such stimulation is currently envisaged. A moratorium on inspections and fines was announced at the beginning of Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine, but it has now been lifted. Ukrainian crypto exchanges worked in the gray zone in anticipation of regulation, and cooperated with the authorities, but there is still no regulation, and claims of the authorities to the exchanges due to work in the gray zone are already emerging.

In general, it is stated that legislators are not very interested in the needs of web3 business and its expertise. A typical case: a Ukrainian web3 company participates in the development of European blockchain infrastructure, cooperates with the UAE in the area of licensing web3 companies, and participates in the development of regulation of the virtual assets market of Bahrain, but there is no demand for such expertise from the Ukrainian regulatory authorities.

Respondents who participated in working groups on the development of the law on virtual assets and pilot projects consider the results of these activities unsatisfactory. The founders are skeptical about the prospects of dialogue with regulatory bodies and the possibility of influencing the rules of the game. The risks that these rules may be changed at any time without taking into account the interests of web3 business are assessed as significant.

MiCA

Ukraine is not ready for MiCA: neither the Ukrainian virtual asset market, public authorities, nor experts. Ukraine does not need a copy of MiCA, but regulatory arbitrage in comparison with MiCA. One of Ukraine's competitive advantages may be the legalization of DAOs.

MiCA is intended to be a single system of regulatory norms for the entire EU so that there is no regulatory arbitrage within the EU. This is a complex regulatory system, which was adopted after five years of development of the crypto-asset market in the EU and licensing of service providers related to virtual assets. MiCA compliance is affordable only for large companies.

Ukraine is not ready to establish a MiCA equivalent. The market is still too young for such strict requirements, regulatory bodies do not have the necessary expertise and resources, and the expert community is not sufficiently developed.

In general, founders agree that clear and transparent rules of the game will benefit the market, even though one of the reasons for Ukraine's leadership in the cryptocurrency usage rankings is the lack of regulation. At the same time, the respondents are unanimous that it is a bad idea to simply repeat MiCA — Ukraine needs regulatory arbitrage even compared to MiCA. Otherwise, when choosing between MiCA in the EU and MiCA in Ukraine with its specific risks and limitations, web3 companies will have no incentive to choose the Ukrainian jurisdiction. Web3 companies can quite easily incorporate in 0% tax jurisdictions, some countries have no capital gains tax on crypto assets. The high mobility of web3 startups can also work in the opposite direction if Ukraine creates attractive conditions for them.

One of the competitive advantages of the Ukrainian jurisdiction could be the legalization of DAOs. In MiCA there is no concept of DAO. Currently, there are only a few jurisdictions in the world where DAOs can be registered. Ukraine did not become one of the first countries in the world with a regulated market of virtual assets, but now it has a chance to be among the first countries that allow the registration of DAOs, the launch of DAO management tokens, and their initial offering. It is desirable that all this can be done online. Ukrainian web3 companies already have technical solutions for launching and managing DAOs.

Regulatory Sandbox

Young web3 startups need a regulatory sandbox. This will lower the entry threshold for web3 founders and increase the pace of the creation of web3 startups in Ukraine.

For a young startup, meeting all the regulatory and licensing requirements is a daunting task in terms of resources. A regulatory sandbox is needed, where web3 startups will be able to launch their products without fear, without waiting for the necessary laws to start their activities, work under simplified conditions for several years, and then, in case of success, get a license and switch to a general regulatory system. Now startups are forced to use the individual entrepreneur regime as a kind of "sandbox".

The regulatory bodies can start with minimum requirements, allow new web3 companies to appear, and gradually adjust these requirements, responding to changes in the market (an example can be the approach of the British Financial Conduct Authority).

Incubation and acceleration of projects can be carried out based on the regulatory sandbox. This will increase the quality of sandbox-resident startups and make it easier for them to attract investment.

Virtual assets as a medium of exchange

The ban on the use of virtual assets as a means of exchange for goods and services almost completely blocks the functioning and development of the web3 economy.

The provision "virtual assets are not a means of payment on the territory of Ukraine and cannot be the subject of exchange for property (goods), work (services)" significantly limits the circulation of crypto assets and the development of the web3 economy.

Not only the sale of physical goods and services for crypto assets but also any exchange of crypto assets for crypto assets, since any crypto assets are property in one way or another, is prohibited. The situation is similar to the increasingly popular lending of real businesses with stablecoins.

If the payments of fees to decentralized applications and custodial services, which are charged to users in crypto assets, are considered payments for services, such applications and services become violators of the law. If the payment of fees for on-chain transactions is interpreted as the use of cryptocurrency to pay for the services of miners or validators, then no cryptocurrency transaction will be legally possible.

There are no such restrictions on the circulation of virtual assets in the USA, Canada, EU, Great Britain, Switzerland, Singapore, Japan, and Australia.

Licensing and standardization

Licensing and standardization are a necessary stage in the development of web3 technologies and the web3 economy, which strengthen the protection of the interests of investors and consumers. Professional associations can take on the role of developing standards for web products, professionals, and education.

Licensing and regular auditing of custodial services are necessary — without them, investors, consumers, and the ecosystem in general bear significant risks. At the same time, it is desirable for a business that plays by the rules to face government authorities only once — when obtaining a license. During licensing, the state should not just charge a fee for the right to enter the market but provide a real service for checking projects for compliance with technical and non-technical standards.

Even those founders who consider licensing for web3 an outdated approach agree with the need for standardization, but by specialized associations, not by the government.

The lack of strict standards for young technology is normal, it stimulates the market to find the best solution. Standards arise in the market spontaneously, as it matures, and the role of the government is to fix them, and not to impose its decisions on the market.

Standardization of web3 technologies and risk assessment of web3 products is a necessary condition for attracting large investors to the industry, who need a clear understanding of all risks, as well as for better consumer protection.

Young startups may not have a sufficient understanding of employee qualification requirements, resulting in wasted time and money by hiring non-professionals. There are many fraudsters and simply unqualified providers of educational services on the market - consumers get a negative experience and become disappointed in web3. Professional associations can undertake certification of specialists and educational products in the field of web3.

Another way to fight against fraudsters and low-quality web3 products is through rating and reputation systems.

Positioning of Ukraine in the Web3 Space

Ukraine needs to decide on its positioning in the web3 world and build its web3 development strategy to follow. The country now has a resource in the form of relatively inexpensive technical talent that needs to be preserved, retained, and turned into successful web3 product companies. There are a number of tools for attracting web3 companies to the Ukrainian jurisdiction. However, without solving the basic problems with the image of Ukraine as a rule-of-law and business-friendly state, these tools may be ineffective.

Currently, Ukraine in the web3 world is primarily a source of cheap technical talent. From the point of view of the added value created by outsourcing companies compared to product companies, such a "resource digital economy" may not be the most effective model for the development of the Ukrainian digital economy in the long term.

Developed outsourcing companies and access to capital are the basis for the emergence of product web3 companies. On the Ukrainian labor market, there is currently a large supply of developers at more affordable prices than a few years ago, which makes it easier to launch product companies. It is easier for Ukrainian founders to work with Ukrainian developers.

Identifying and mastering new technological directions and the rules of the game for them is the basis of the country's development. Ukraine needs to decide on its position in the web3 world and make it the basis of the strategy for the development of the Ukrainian web3 economy. Since positioning is part of marketing, it may be useful to involve not only government and web3 business representatives but also professional marketers (Estonia is an example of a jurisdiction where marketing has helped to increase the attractiveness of web3 companies).

The web3 development strategy in Ukraine may include:

- development and strengthening of the infrastructure for the digital economy (in particular, increasing the coverage and penetration of the Internet),
- support for the development of all elements of the startup ecosystem,
- joint investment programs of the state and venture funds in Ukrainian web3 startups,
- stimulation of product web3 businesses,
- encouraging young Ukrainian web3 specialists to stay in the country,
- emphasis on comprehensive support of startups in the most promising areas of web3 (for example, DeFi, tokenization of assets),
- legalization of DAOs and the sale of their management tokens (in particular, for stablecoins),
- the ability to attract investments in stablecoins (and not pay taxes on these investments), pay employees and counterparties with these stablecoins, open a bank account and transfer fiat from the sale of these stablecoins to it,
- special conditions for industrial mining,
- implementation of web3 technologies in public administration and services,
- support and partnership projects with professional associations,
- the simplest possible legislation and taxation,
- regulatory arbitration,
- digital residency for digital nomads.

The choice of priorities depends on what Ukraine wants to be in the world of web3.

Foreign investors have already understood the difference between Ukrainians and Russians, but they still have a cautious attitude towards teams from the post-Soviet space due to the large number of fraudulent projects from this region. There are Ukrainian startups to which American investors recommended adding Americans, Europeans, or Asians to the team for greater respectability. Several respondents noted that even among the representatives of the Ukrainian web3 community sometimes a toxic attitude towards Ukrainian founders occurs.

The founders themselves have to work on their image and thus create a collective image of Ukrainian web3 startups, but nothing prevents the government from looking for ways to help them with this. The same with the formation of loyalty of Ukrainian users to Ukrainian brands. There are successful Ukrainian IT startups, but how many Ukrainians know about them?

Cultural initiatives are an important tool for shaping the country's image. Ukrainian artists experimenting with web3 technologies have been contributing to the image of Ukraine for many years, but now it is happening spontaneously, without any strategy, and in the complete absence of interest and support from official cultural institutions.

There are also more general problems: web3 businesses and investors still do not perceive Ukraine as a rule-of-law and business-friendly state, and there is still low trust in the law enforcement and judicial system. Strong bureaucracy in decision-making and problems with corruption are noted. There is an opinion that without progress in solving these problems, it makes no sense to talk about the development of the web3 economy in Ukraine.

Web3 for the state

Ukraine is ahead of many developed countries in the level of digitalization (online banking, public services), and web3 technologies can strengthen its leadership in this area. There are many web3 projects, promising from the point of view of economic and social effects, which can be launched by the state in the form of pilots.

The most popular answer to the question "How can web3 technologies improve public administration?" is transparent and falsification-resistant public registers and voting. Web3 technologies can reduce costs and strengthen the elements of direct democracy and citizen participation in the distribution of budget funds at all levels. Initially, these solutions can be implemented as pilots in small communities. A condition for the implementation of web3 technologies in public governance and services is a comprehensive study of the risks they carry.

Other ideas expressed by respondents:

- Central Bank Digital Currency (CBDC),
- the use of web3 technologies for storing and processing medical data as a means of combating abuse and protecting the personal data of patients,

- web3-ID based on zero-knowledge proof,
- simplifying the work of an electronic digital signature thanks to the use of a cryptocurrency wallet for this purpose,
- jury trial using digital IDs and zero-knowledge proof for mitigation of the juror pressure risk.
- electronic queues in official institutions using decentralized registers and digital signatures,
- a decentralized platform for conducting public tenders,
- tokenization for more transparent and effective privatization of state-owned companies and their management.
- tokenization of intellectual rights for museums and NFT stamps for Ukrposhta.

There are fears that the implementation of web3 technologies in public services may not have adequate support from officials for several reasons: misunderstanding of the value of these solutions for the country, reduction of the bureaucracy as a result of digitization, and blocking of possible corruption schemes. Technologies cannot solve anything without social progress, without a corresponding social contract. There are countries that managed to significantly reduce the level of corruption even before the advent of computers.

Mass Adoption

The mass adoption of web3 depends not only on communicating the benefits and risks of web3 technologies to the broad masses of users but also on the increase in the number of web3 products that solve real problems of the mass user, on the convenience of these products and the willingness of users to pay for them. It also depends on the companies that implement web3 technologies in their products and business processes, and therefore on the awareness of the general business community about the benefits and risks of implementing web3 technologies.

Ukraine is among the leaders in the use of cryptocurrencies. Among the factors of this success, the following can be distinguished: lack of strict regulation, fast and cheap cross-border transfers, opportunities to invest in the global stock market; the willingness of the population to accept high risks for the chance to quickly receive additional income (in particular, due to low incomes of the population); relatively low trust to the government and the traditional financial system.

Despite the high position of Ukraine in the ranking of the use of cryptocurrencies, the founders do not agree on the number of Ukrainian web3 users and the attractiveness of the Ukrainian market for web3 companies. Some believe that there are enough retail users, some that there are not enough of them, and the outflow of web3 specialists from the country will lead to an even greater decline. There is agreement about the low paying capacity of retail web3 users, but the assessment of the attractiveness of the Ukrainian retail market varies: "attractive for many companies", "attractive only for large global companies", and "no one is interested".

Today, the vast majority of web3 users are not users in the literal sense of the word. Mostly, these are investors in virtual assets and "test" users who use web3 products only while receiving a reward for it. So far, the web3 ecosystem is one big venture project: most startups are solving problems that don't exist yet.

Due to the focus of projects on user-investors, satisfaction of the needs of real users recedes into the background. A clear example is the GameFi segment, where the component Fi (finance) is often present, but Game is not. There are few real web3 users because there are few web3 products that solve real problems for the mass user. The UX of web3 products leaves much to be desired, and users' trust in these products is still far from trust in Big Tech companies. This lack of trust is connected, in particular, with the lack of a clear position of the government regarding web3 and its participation in the protection of consumer rights.

Increasing internet coverage and penetration, basic financial, digital, and web3 literacy are drivers of mass web3 adoption, but at the end of the day, users care about the products, not the technologies they are built on. Mass adoption of web3 is when people don't even know they are using these technologies in their daily lives, i.e. the abstraction of web3 technologies from the end user. In this sense, mass adoption of Web3 technologies no longer depends on users, but on companies that implement these technologies in their everyday products and business processes.

A precondition for mass adoption is mass awareness. Entrepreneurs from various industries, sometimes very far from the world of cryptocurrencies and the digital economy, need to understand exactly how web3 technologies can be useful for their business. This is not a quick process, especially if it happens spontaneously, and uncoordinated, but it continues. In 20-30 years, all IT systems will use these technologies.

CONCLUSION

This report does not intend to be a comprehensive and exhaustive coverage of the challenges and opportunities facing the web3 space in Ukraine. Its task is to convey to all stakeholders the perspectives of Ukrainian Web3 founders, which are highly relevant in assessing the potential of the space, and to initiate public discussion.

The web3 founders who took part in this series of interviews are very diverse and often in disagreement: there are engineering, business, and humanities backgrounds; first-time founders and experienced ones; key figures in the global web3 community and unknown entrepreneurs; anarcho-capitalists and supporters of reasonable government regulation; optimists and pessimists, sceptics and cheerleaders. However, despite the many differences, all participants were committed to the future of Ukraine and each actively contributes, in one way or another, to a positive future for their country.

Dialogue is primarily the ability to listen and hear the interlocutor, based on the desire to reach mutual understanding, and to cooperate to find a solution. The main conclusion of our research: the talent, experience, and expertise of Ukrainian web3 founders deserve to be heard. We hope that this report, which the Web3 Institute intends to publish annually, supports a considerate dialogue between regulatory authorities and founders in Ukraine.

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